

Supporting Information

Elemental trade-off in the selective Electrooxidation of Ethylene Glycol on Palladium-Silver/Nickel Electrodes

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Figure S1. Photos of the electrodes prepared by electrodeposition method.

Figure S2. Cyclic voltammograms of Pd₈₁Ag₁₉@NF (2 cm²_{geo}) and Pd₇₉Ag₂₁@NF (4 cm²_{geo}) in 0.1 M EG + 1 M KOH.

Figure S3. Cyclic voltammograms of Pd₂₄Ag₇₆@NF (1 mg/cm²), Pd₅₂Ag₄₈@NF (5 mg/cm²) and Pd₇₆Ag₂₄@NF (1 mg/cm²) in 0.1 M EG + 1 M KOH.

Figure S4. Cyclic voltammograms of Pd₇₆Ag₂₄@NF in 1 M KOH (grey) and 0.1 M EG + 1 M KOH (red).

Figure S5. Equivalent circuit used for EIS data fitting, where R_s is the solution resistance, R_{ct} the charge transfer resistance, CPE_{dl} is a constant phase element corresponding to the double layer capacitance. CPE_{ads} and R_{ads} are related to the adsorption of reactants and L is an inductor.

Figure S6. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 13.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S7. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₂₄Ag₇₆@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 8.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S8. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₃₇Ag₆₃@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 19.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S9. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₅₂Ag₄₈@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S10. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₆₇Ag₃₃@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 42.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S11. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₇₆Ag₂₄@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 2.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S12. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₇₉Ag₂₁@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 44.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S13. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₈₁Ag₁₉@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$).

Figure S14. EIS fitting of a) the Bode diagram and b) the Nyquist plot of Pd₉₃Ag₇@NF. Levenberg-Marquardt method fitting ($\chi^2 = 8.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Figure S15. Time resolved HPLC chromatograms of the 24 h electrolysis with Pd₇₆Ag₂₄@NF at 0.705 V. a) RID detector and b) VWD detector.

Figure S16. Time resolved HPLC chromatograms of the 6 h electrolysis with Pd₇₆Ag₂₄@NF at 0.92 V. a) RID detector and b) VWD detector.

Figure S17. Cyclic voltammograms of Pd@NF_{solv} in 0.6 M EG + 1 M KOH with the electrolysis potential indicated at 0.9 V.

Figure S18. Ethylene glycol in electrolyte over 141 h electrolysis with Pd@NF_{solv}.

Figure S19. Potential profile of the 141 h electrolysis with Pd@NF_{solv}, showing the “refreshing” of the electrode.

Figure S20. Photos of Pd@NF_{solv} where a) shows the whole electrode, and b) and c) are optical microscopy photos at 50× and 500× magnification, respectively.